

ADVERSITY QUOTIENT OF PUBLIC-SCHOOL PRINCIPALS IN HINABANGAN, WESTERN SAMAR: EFFECTS ON DEMOGRAPHICS AND SCHOOL PERFORMANCE

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Adversity Quotient of Public-School Principals in Hinabangan, Western Samar: Effects on Demographics and School Performance

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Abstract

This study investigated the Adversity Quotient (AQ) of school heads in selected public schools. The research aimed to determine the AQ levels of school heads, identify factors influencing AQ, and explore potential management guides to enhance and sustain AQ. The study involved school heads, all of whom were female, with an average age of 41 years old and above and more than two years of experience as school heads. Demographic data revealed that a majority of the respondents held doctorate units, were married, and earned a monthly net salary exceeding 50,000 pesos. The AQ assessment employed the Adversity Response Profile (ARP), measuring four core dimensions: Control, Ownership, Reach, and Endurance. Results indicated a high overall AQ, with the highest scores in Ownership, followed by Endurance, Reach, and Control. Further analysis revealed no significant correlation between AQ and demographic variables such as age, civil status, educational attainment, or approximate monthly salary. This suggests that AQ is not solely determined by these factors.

Keywords: *user-centered, word game-based, approach in teaching, pupils' learning achievement*

Introduction

According to the International Standard Classification of Education (ISCED), basic education comprises the two stages primary education and lower secondary education. According to the definition of the Implementing Rules and Regulations of Republic Act 9155, basic education is the education intended to meet basic learning needs which lays the foundation on which subsequent learning can be based. It encompasses early childhood, elementary and high school education as well as alternative learning systems for out-of-school youth and adult learners and includes education for those with special needs. This includes kindergarten up to Grade 12 (K to 12). This includes elementary education, junior high school education, and senior high school education, plus alternative learning systems, special education and other related terms.

The school principal also called school head or academic head or administrative head are persons responsible for the administrative and instructional supervision of the school or cluster of schools (IRR RA 9155). He must fully know how to manage various adversities and problems always accompanied in the chosen administrative position. He should have high level of intelligence quotient, emotional quotient and as well as adversity quotient to maintain excellence and run the academic and administrative aspects of the school smoothly.

In instructional supervision and school governance, the school head is a person with significant authority over academic and administrative functions in the school.

Elisabeth Kubler-Ross once said: "The most beautiful people we have known are those who have known defeat, known suffering, known struggle, known loss, and have found their way out of the depths. These persons have an appreciation, a sensitivity, and an understanding of life that fills them with compassion, gentleness, and a deep loving concern. Beautiful people do not just happen."

Abraham Lincoln also said: "Nearly all men can stand adversity, but if we want to test a man's character, give him power."

Og Mandino also said: "Remind thyself, in the darkest moments, that every failure is only a step toward success, every detection of what is false directs you toward what is true, every trial exhausts some tempting form of error, and every adversity will only hide, for a time, your path to peace and fulfillment."

Statements above deal with adversity and how adversity is turned into a blessing.

How these problems, adversities and complexities are resolved is highly dependent upon the individual's dean's personal qualities express in style of leadership and the level of adversity quotient they possess. As the recognized leader in a particular academic unit in higher education institution, a dean has a lot of responsibilities and accountability in the organization. The position is critical to the organizational development and academic growth of the students, because the dean is usually the main source and the driving force that sustains the welfare of the organization (Williams, 2003).

As politically susceptible leadership issues continue to be on the forefront of tertiary education, it is imperative that research measures the level of adversity quotient and examines the responses of deans of nursing schools to adversity as the new area of leadership training. The multi-faceted roles of being school heads of public schools could exert too much pressure on their psychological and social well-being, which in turn, could jeopardize the gainful existence of the school.

Educational leadership roles according to Law and Glover (2000) take the form of being leading professionals who act as mentor,

educator, advisor, ambassador, and advocate, and of being chief executive, who act as strategist, manager, arbitrator, executive officer and diplomat.

If a school head of a particular public school has low adversity quotient (AQ) in spite of his higher IQ and EQ, he may eventually end up resigning from his post, committing suicide or being kicked out due to conflict of principle or related misunderstandings.

Very often, the school heads' existing capacity (what they have) could not equal the required capacity (what the school demands) to do the task, thus creating a gap in their performance. School heads who experienced a persistent gap between their existing capacity and the required capacity is an indication of their inability to fulfil their potential, in consequence, lowering their performance in terms of resourcefulness, adjustment to change with new ideas, problem solving, decision making, optimism and healthiness. Most deans are stressed by the chronic burden imposed by the demands to perform to their utmost human capacity, only to fall short of what is demanded when it matters most.

Currently, aside from political pressures, school heads are facing many issues and emergent adversities with which educational leaders must contend. Emergent adversities such as academic problems, fraternities and sororities, drug addictions, early pregnancy, parental problems, bullying, discipline, tardiness and absenteeism among learners and faculty members are the most common. In addition to this, advances and changes in technology, science, moral values, environment, and continuous accreditation, conformance to international standards, and international relationship and linkages hold a varied assortment of challenges and adversities in basic education.

How a leader responds to these adversities not only affects the leader's performance but also the performance of those being led. Learning to deal with adversity in the organization in one's career life is an essential element of effective leadership (Wallington, 2004).

The researcher was greatly challenged to conduct a study to measure the adversity quotient of school heads in order to formulate suggested management guides and techniques to ensure higher level of AQ among educational leaders of basic education schools. According to Stoltz' Theory, leaders with high adversity quotient respond most effectively to adversity and will prevail in work and in life thereby becoming the leaders of today and tomorrow.

This study would provide research-based information on the profile of school heads of basic education schools. Essential information is to be gathered to help in discovering the school heads' hidden resource that could spell success or failure in their leadership, performance and practices. Through this study, the researcher will be able to determine the level of adversity quotient, the types of educational leadership that are currently in use by them. The researcher found it very interesting to study the AQ of the school heads of selected public schools, because of the nature of their job which requires them to work closely with stakeholders as well as their clientele- the learners without sacrificing the quality of education and conformity of the school with the standards of education being promulgated by the DepEd- Central Office.

Research Questions

The main purpose of this study is to measure the adversity quotient or level of resiliency among the school heads of selected public schools in Hinabangan, Western Samar, which would be the basis for formulation of management guides and techniques to strengthen and sustain school performance. Specifically, it attempts to answer the following sub-problems:

1. What is the demographic profile of respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. gender;
 - 1.3. civil status;
 - 1.4. highest educational attainment;
 - 1.5. place of residence;
 - 1.6. religion;
 - 1.7. number of years as a school head
 - 1.8. number of years of administrative experience;
 - 1.9. name of the school managed;
 - 1.10. approximate total monthly gross salary range?
2. What is the adversity quotient of the school heads in terms of:
 - 2.1. control;
 - 2.2. ownership;
 - 2.3. reach; and
 - 2.4. endurance?
3. How may the adversity quotient of the respondents be measured in terms of:
 - 3.1. internal concerns;
 - 3.2. external concerns?
4. Is there significant relationship on the responses of the school heads regarding adversity quotient when they are grouped according to demographic profile?

5. Based on the findings of the study, what suggested management guides and techniques may be formulated to augment and sustain their level of adversity quotient?

Methodology

Research Design

The researcher of this thesis intends to use the descriptive- assessment-survey type of research using cross-sectional research study.

Wikipedia introduces descriptive research, as statistical research which describes data and characteristics about the population or phenomenon being studied. Descriptive research answers the questions who, what, where, when and how.

Wikipedia reveals that although the data description is factual, accurate and systematic, the research cannot describe what caused a situation. Thus, descriptive research cannot be used to create a causal relationship, where one variable affects another. In other words, descriptive research can be said to have a low requirement for internal validity.

Descriptive research is the most commonly used research method. And the basic reason for carrying out descriptive research is to identify the cause of something that is happening. It includes studies that purport to present facts concerning nature and status of anything. This means that descriptive method of research gives meaning to the quality and standing of facts that are going on.

Ardales (2008) says that descriptive research describes “what is” and involves description, recording, analysis, and interpretation of the present nature, composition or processes of phenomena. This type of research focuses on prevailing conditions or how a person, group and thing behaves or functions in the present. It also deals with comparison and contrast.

It also consists of identifying and defining a problem, selecting appropriate sources of data, adopting appropriate technique for the data gathering procedures, analyzing, interpreting and describing data. Descriptive method focuses at the present condition. Its purpose is to find new truth. The truth referred here may have many different forms such as increased quantity of knowledge, a new generation or new “law”, increased insights into factors which are operating, a new accurate formation of the problem to be solved and many others.

Descriptive studies are of large value in providing facts, which base scientific judgment. In descriptive studies, numerous instruments are employed. For instance, test, questionnaire, interviews, observation schedules, checklists scorecards and rating scales.

Calmorin, et.al. (2007) describes the survey as a non-experimental, descriptive research method. Survey studies research- is a measurement process using a highly structured interview. It employs a measurement tool called a questionnaire, measurement instrument, or interview schedule. This type is suitable wherever the subjects vary among themselves and one is interested to know the extent to which different conditions and situations are obtained among these subjects. The word survey signifies the gathering of data regarding present conditions. A survey is useful in providing the value of facts, and focusing attention on the most important things to be reported.

The survey research design is often used because of the low cost and easy accessible information. The survey research design is a very valuable tool for assessing opinions and trends. Even on a small scale, such as local government or small businesses, judging opinion with carefully designed surveys can dramatically change strategies. Surveys can be useful when a researcher wants to collect data on phenomena that cannot be directly observed. there is no way of achieving 100% accuracy. Opinions, on all levels, are very fluid and can change on a daily or even hourly basis.

Despite this, surveys are still a powerful tool and can be an extremely powerful research tool. As long as you design your survey well and are prepared to be self-critical, you can still obtain an accurate representation of opinion.

Assessment studies research, on the other hand describes the status of a phenomenon at a particular time. It describes without value judgment a prevailing situation. It attempts no explanation of underlying reasons and makes no recommendations for action.

In this study, cross-sectional survey type was used. Cross-sectional surveys are used to gather information on a population at a single point in time (Babbie 2006).

Cross-sectional research differs from a longitudinal research in that cross-sectional studies are designed to look at a variable at a particular point in time. While longitudinal studies involve taking multiple measures over an extended period of time, cross-sectional research is focused on finding relationships between variables at a specific point in time.

Respondents

Sampling is a process of choosing a representative part of the population under study. It can also be defined as the process whereby a subset of items is picked from a set, and done so using a systematic process.

In other words, sampling in the context of social science and education means using a randomization technique to pick respondents from a larger population, and through that technique removing selection and other bases. The reason for sampling is that a researcher can gain accurate knowledge about a population by measuring only a portion- or a sample of it. Besides, it includes the total number

of population.

In this study, purposive-census sampling technique will be used. This type of sampling will be used for the selection of expected respondents. A sample only the school heads of the selected public schools were chosen as respondents. Purposive sampling is based on what the researcher chooses the sample based on who she thinks would be appropriate for the study. In this study, only the school heads of the Hinabangan, Western Samar qualify as respondents for her study.

This researcher selected school heads in Hinabangan, Western Samar as respondents. The researcher validated and statistically analyzed the raw data gathered from the questionnaire of the respondents.

Procedure

Permission to conduct the study will be first sought from the Schools Division Superintendent before any part of this research be started. The researcher personally distributed the questionnaire to the twelve (12) respondents at their respective offices in their schools at a certain period of time (around second to third weeks of May, 2023) in their scheduled time and set schedule to get them back for them to have ample time to respond to the questions.

The researcher personally retrieved them in order for her to check on the accuracy and consistency of the answers and conducted unstructured interviews to supplement the data she will gather from the questionnaire. The respondents were given option not to write their names. In this way, they will feel free and more comfortable to give their accurate and honest answers. All distributed questionnaires were retrieved in one-week time to give respondents sufficient time to answer the questionnaire at their own pace.

Prior to the conduct of the study, the researcher secured the permission of Dr. Paul Stoltz to use the Adversity Response Profile® in measuring the Adversity Quotient® level of the respondents. After approval of the request, the signing the Terms of Agreement were done. The researcher prepared the letters of request for concerned school heads seeking permission to conduct the study. After approval of the request, the researcher personally administered and retrieved the questionnaires from the target respondents. The gathered data were classified, encoded and summarized. Then, the researcher analyzed and interpreted the findings of the study following the sequence of the problems posed in Chapter 1 with the help of a statistician.

Ethical Considerations

Considering the fact that participants are human beings, strict ethical considerations will be observed; the researcher will ensure that the school heads' health and rights will not be harmed. The primary concern of the researcher should be the safety of the research participant. This will be accomplished by carefully considering the risk/benefit ratio, using all available information to make an appropriate assessment and continually monitoring the research as it proceeds. Since this study is harmless in nature, there is no problem in regards to possible harm.

Autonomy involves self-determination and freedom. Autonomy is the right of everyone to cover identity and to generate personal decisions independently. Each and every pupil has the right to refuse intervention if it is against their will. Allowing the sample whether to accept or refuse the intervention with consideration (Beauchamp, 2001). Since the intervention is purely harmless and educational in nature, there is no problem of invoking autonomy.

Confidentiality safeguards the trust of clients that information learned in the context of a professional relationship is shared outside the educational institution with the client's permission or as legally required. Right of anonymity must also be respected if the client invokes such right. The researcher must enumerate how privacy and confidentiality concerns will be approached. The researcher must be sensitive to not only how information is protected from unauthorized observation, but also if and how participants are to be notified of any unforeseen findings from the research that they may or may not want to know. The principle of beneficence addresses deeds of mercy kindness and charity. Beneficence means taking action to promote the welfare of other people, the manipulation seeks the purpose of the study should be explained to the participants and discusses its possible effect.

Non-malificence means to do no harm and is considered to be an over-riding principle for everyone who undertakes any experimental research study (Munson, 2004). It is the responsibility of the researchers for whatever happens to the research participant after the initial intervention so we must be cautious not to harm the research participant or cause anything that will degrade the subjects' well-being. Honesty and integrity are also two important terms. The researcher maintains the highest level of honesty and integrity. Imaginary research and hocus-focus method have no part in this study.

Results and Discussion

Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Age

Table 1 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents in terms of age. This table shows that out of 10 respondents, 3 or 30% are 41 to 45 years old; 3 or 30% are 61 and above years old; 2 or 20% are 46 to 50 years old; 1 or 10% is 51 to 55 years old; and 1 or 10% is 56 to 60 years old. This implies that all of the respondents are forties to sixties.

Table 1. *Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents in Terms of Age*

Age	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Rank
41 to 45	3	30	1.5
46 to 50	2	20	3
51 to 55	1	10	4.5
56 to 60	1	10	4.5
61 and above	3	30	1.5
Total	10	100.00	

Gender

Table 2. *Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents in Terms of Gender*

Gender	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Rank
Male	0	0	-
Female	10	100	1
Total	10	100.00	

Table 2 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents in terms of gender. This table shows that out of 10 respondents, 10 or 100% of the respondents are female. This implies that all respondents are female- a proof that education field is dominated by female.

Civil Status

Table 3. *Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents in Terms of Civil Status*

Civil Status	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Rank
Single	2	20	2
Married	7	70	1
Widow/Widower	1	10	3
Total	10	100.00	

Table 3 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents in terms of civil status. This table shows that out of 10 respondents, 7 or 70% are married; 2 or 20% are single and 1 or 10% is a widow. Majority of the respondents are married.

Education Attainment

Table 4. *Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents in Terms of Highest Educational Attainment*

Highest Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Rank
MA Degree Holder	3	30	2
With Doctorate Units	6	60	1
Doctorate Degree Holder	1	10	3
Total	10	100.00	

Table 4 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents in terms of highest educational attainment. This table shows that out of 10 respondents, 6 or 60% are with doctorate units; 3 or 30% are MA degree holders only; and 1 or 10% is a doctorate degree holder. This implies that majority of the respondents have doctorate units.

Place of Residence

Table 5. *Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents in Terms of Place of Residence*

Place of Residence	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Rank
A	4	40	1
B	1	10	4.5
C	1	10	4.5
D	1	10	4.5
E	1	10	4.5
F	1	10	4.5
G	1	10	4.5
Total	10	100.00	

Table 5 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents in terms of place of residence. This table shows that out of 10 respondents, 4 or 40% reside in A; 1 or 10% reside in B; 1 or 10% reside in C; 1 or 10% reside in D; 1 or 10% reside in E; 1 or 10% reside in F; 1 or 10% reside in G. Almost half of the respondents reside in A. The rest reside in various places in Hinabangan, Western Samar. In this case the researcher was requested to keep their place of residences in anonymity for confidential purposes.

Religion

Table 6. *Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents in Terms of Religion*

<i>Religion</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>	<i>Rank</i>
Roman Catholic	8	80	1
Iglesia ni Cristo	1	10	2.5
Protestant	1	10	2.5
Total	10	100.00	

Table 6 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents in terms of religion. This table shows that out of 10 respondents, 8 or 80% are Roman Catholic; 1 or 10% is a member of Iglesia ni Cristo and 1 or 10% is a protestant. This implies that majority of the respondents are Roman Catholic.

Number of Years as School Head

Table 7. *Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents in Terms of Number of Years as School Head*

<i>Number of Years as School Head</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>	<i>Rank</i>
Less than 1	0	0	-
1	0	0	-
2	0	0	-
More than 2	10	100	1
Total	10	100.00	

Table 7 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents in terms of number of years as school head. This table shows that out of 10 respondents, 10 or 100% have more than 2 years of being school head. This implies that all respondents have more than 2 years of being a school head.

Number of Years of Administrative Experiences

Table 8. *Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents in Terms of Number of Years of Administrative Experiences*

<i>Number of Years of Administrative Experiences</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>	<i>Rank</i>
Less than 1	0	0	-
1	0	0	-
2	0	0	-
More than 2	10	100	1
Total	10	100.00	

Table 8 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents in terms of number of years of administrative experiences. This table shows that out of 10 respondents, 10 or 100% have more than 2 years of administrative experiences. This implies that all respondents have more than 2 years of administrative experiences.

Names of the Universities/Colleges

Table 9. *Names of the Universities/Colleges the Deans belong*

<i>Name of the School Managed</i>
A1
B2
C3
D4
E5
F6
G7
H8
I9
J10

Table 9 presents the names of the schools the respondents belong. They are arranged alphabetically. Here are the names of the schools used in the study. The respondents that the names of their schools be put in anonymity for the purpose of confidentiality. These are: A1, B2, C3, D4, E5, F6, G7, H8, I9, J10.

Total Monthly Net Salary

Table 10. *Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents in Terms of Approximate Total Monthly Net Salary*

Approximate Total Monthly Net Salary (Php)	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Rank
30,001 to 35,000	2	20	2
35,001-40,000	1	10	3.5
40,001-45,000	1	10	3.5
50,001 and above	6	60	1
Total	10	100.00	

Table 10 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents in terms of number of years of administrative experiences. This table shows that out of 10 respondents, 6 or 60% receive an approximate monthly gross salary of more than 50,000 pesos; 2 or 20% receive 30,001 to 35,000 pesos; 1 or 10% receives 35,001 to 40,000 pesos and 1 or 10% receives 40,001 to 45,000 pesos. This implies that majority of the school heads in said province receive an approximate monthly net salary of more than fifty thousand pesos.

Adversity Quotient of the School Heads in terms of

Control

Table 11. *Frequency, Summation and Mean Distribution of Responses of Respondents to determine their Adversity Quotient in Terms of Control*

Indicators	5	4	3	2	1	$\sum x$	$\sum xw$	Mean
1. I do not bring problems at work when going home.	5	0	2	3	00	10	37	3.70
2. I consider problems as part of life and I do not allow myself to be affected with it.	0	4	0	2	44	10	24	2.40
3. If something bad happen to me, I try to recover as soon as possible.	3	6	1	0	00	10	42	4.20
4. I sleep early at night although I have more things to finish.	0	2	6	1	11	10	29	2.90
5. I regularly exercise before I go to my office.	1	3	5	1	00	10	34	3.40
6. I practice balanced diet on time, more on fruits and vegetables, big in the morning and little at night.	3	1	5	1	00	10	36	3.60
7. I also inhale a lot of fresh air, expose myself on sunlight moderately and drink a lot of water to ensure maximum health.	3	3	4	0	00	10	39	3.90
8. I never smoke cigarette nor drink liquor nor do any evil vices.	10	0	0	0	00	10	50	5.00
9. I'm very determined to do something I think right and with a specific purpose.	9	1	0	0	00	10	49	4.90
10. I resolve problems that arise at work and with persistence and diligence, I try to normalize succeeding situations caused by the problems.	5	5	0	0	00	10	45	4.50
Composite Mean								3.85

Table 11.1. *Mean and Percentile Distribution of Responses of Respondents to determine their Adversity Quotient in Terms of Control*

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Percentile Equivalent	Verbal Description	Interpretation	Rank
1. I do not bring problems at work when going home.	3.70	87	Agree	High	6
2. I consider problems as part of life and I do not allow myself to be affected with it.	2.40	74	Disagree	Low	10
3. If something bad happen to me, I try to recover as soon as possible.	4.20	92	Agree	High	4
4. I sleep early at night although I have more things to finish.	2.90	79	Moderately agree	Average	9
5. I regularly exercise before I go to my office.	3.40	84	Moderately agree	Average	8
6. I practice balanced diet on time, more on fruits and vegetables, big in the morning and little at night.	3.60	86	Strongly agree	High	7
7. I also inhale a lot of fresh air, expose myself on sunlight moderately and drink a lot of water to ensure maximum health.	3.90	89	Agree	High	5
8. I never smoke cigarette nor drink liquor nor do any evil vices.	5.00	100	Strongly agree	Very high	1

9.	I'm very determined to do something I think right and with a specific purpose.	4.90	99	Strongly agree	Very high	2
10.	I resolve problems that arise at work and with persistence and diligence, I try to normalize succeeding situations caused by the problems.	4.50	95	Strongly agree	Very high	3
Composite Mean		3.85	88	Agree	High	

Table 11 and Table 11.1 present the frequency, summation, mean and percentile distribution of responses of respondents to determine their adversity quotient in terms of control. These tables show that the respondents agree that they have high adversity quotient in terms of control as indicated in the composite mean of 3.85 and percentile equivalent of 88. Control is the extent to which someone perceives they can influence whatever happens next. It determines resilience, health, and tenacity. Among the indicators of AQ-Control, the highest five that greatly characterize the respondents are:

Rank 1: The school heads never smoke cigarette nor drink liquor nor do any evil vices. (Weighted Mean = 5.00 or Percentile Equivalent = 100)

Rank 2: They are very determined to do something they think right and with a specific purpose. (Weighted Mean = 4.90 or Percentile Equivalent = 99)

Rank 3: They resolve problems that arise at work and with persistence and diligence, they try to normalize succeeding situations caused by the problems. (Weighted Mean = 4.50 or Percentile Equivalent = 95)

Rank 4: If something bad happen to them, they try to recover as soon as possible. (Weighted Mean = 4.20 or Percentile Equivalent = 92)

Rank 5: They also inhale a lot of fresh air, expose themselves on sunlight moderately and drink a lot of water to ensure maximum health. (Weighted Mean = 3.90 or Percentile Equivalent = 89)

This implies that the school heads of selected public schools at said province have generally high level of AQ in terms of control. All of them never drink nor smoke or do vices. Majority of them are very determined to do something they think right and with a specific purpose. They resolve problems that arise at work and with persistence and diligence, they try to normalize succeeding situations caused by the problems. If something bad happen to them, they try to recover as soon as possible. They are also concerned with their health. They inhale a lot of fresh air, expose themselves on sunlight moderately and drink a lot of water to ensure maximum health. Most of them do not bring problems at work when going home. Some of them practice balanced diet on time, more on fruits and vegetables, big in the morning and little at night. Unfortunately, they seldom exercise before going to their offices. Most of them sleep late at night due to numerous things to finish. Most of them do not consider problems as part of life and allow themselves to be affected with it. However, their general AQ in terms of control is still high.

Table 12. Frequency, Summation and Mean Distribution of Responses of Respondents to determine their Adversity Quotient in Terms of Ownership

Indicators		5	4	3	2	1	$\sum x$	$\sum xw$	Mean
1.	As a leader, I'm answerable/ accountable to all actions done by myself and all my subordinates and the results. I don't blame others. I assume myself the responsibilities.	9	0	1	0	0	10	48	4.80
2.	It is my obligation to carry forward the assigned task to me to a successful conclusion with authority to direct and take necessary action to ensure success.	45	0	3	0	0	10	49	4.90
3.	I do all what I think best to accomplish the mandate provided to me.	9	1	0	0	0	10	49	4.90
4.	I keep myself busy at work and act all requests at my table as soon as possible to avoid delay.	45	4	0	0	0	10	50	5.00
5.	I do everything I think important to meet all the deadlines and ensure smooth sailing of the organization I manage.	10	0	0	0	0	10	50	5.00
6.	I attend meetings, engagements and prior commitments on time. I ensure that I attend all appointments I have in my schedule on time. In case of conflict of schedule, I delegate such task to my assistant to attend such appointment to represent me without delay.	50	0	0	0	0	10	48	4.80
7.	I attend meetings, engagements and prior commitments on time. I ensure that I attend all appointments I have in my schedule on time. In case of conflict of schedule, I delegate such task to my assistant to attend such appointment to represent me without delay.	8	2	0	0	0	10	48	4.80
8.	I participate as much as possible to all necessary activities of the organization I belong to show to my constituents that I'm visible and ready to serve at any cost.	40	8	0	0	0	10	39	3.90
9.	I also accept wholeheartedly all invitations to speak or grace programs or be a judge in a contest or to provide talks.	2	5	3	0	0	10	46	4.60
10.	When problems at work come, I involve myself to the speedy resolution of the problems.	6	4	0	0	0	10	42	4.20
	If something wrong happen, I do not blame the employees nor anybody who are implicated in that blunder. But I try to correct the system which may be the cause of that problem.	30	16	0	0	0	15	24	3
Composite Mean									4.69

Table 12.1. Mean and Percentile Distribution of Responses of Respondents to determine their Adversity Quotient in Terms of Ownership

	Indicators	Weighted Mean	Percentile Equivalent	Verbal Description	Interpretation	Rank
1.	As a leader, I'm answerable/ accountable to all actions done by myself and all my subordinates and the results. I don't blame others. I assume myself the responsibilities.	4.80	98	Strongly agree	Very high	6
2.	It is my obligation to carry forward the assigned task to me to a successful conclusion with authority to direct and take necessary action to ensure success.	4.90	99	Strongly agree	Very high	3.5
3.	I do all what I think best to accomplish the mandate provided to me.	4.90	99	Strongly agree	Very high	3.5
4.	I keep myself busy at work and act all requests at my table as soon as possible to avoid delay.	5.00	100	Strongly agree	Very high	1.5
5.	I do everything I think important to meet all the deadlines and ensure smooth sailing of the organization I manage.	5.00	100	Strongly agree	Very high	1.5
6.	I attend meetings, engagements and prior commitments on time. I ensure that I attend all appointments I have in my schedule on time. In case of conflict of schedule, I delegate such task to my assistant to attend such appointment to represent me without delay.	4.80	98	Strongly agree	Very high	6
7.	I participate as much as possible to all necessary activities of the organization I belong to show to my constituents that I'm visible and ready to serve at any cost.	4.80	98	Strongly agree	Very high	6
8.	I also accept wholeheartedly all invitations to speak or grace programs or be a judge in a contest or to provide talks.	3.90	89	Agree	High	10
9.	When problems at work come, I involve myself to the speedy resolution of the problems.	4.60	96	Strongly agree	Very high	8
10.	If something wrong happen, I do not blame the employees nor anybody who are implicated in that blunder. But I try to correct the system which may be the cause of that problem.	4.20	92	Agree	High	9
Composite Mean		4.69	96	Strongly agree	Very high	

Table 12 and Table 12.1 present the frequency, summation, mean and percentile distribution of responses of respondents to determine their adversity quotient in terms of ownership. These tables show that the respondents strongly agree that they have high level of adversity quotient (AQ) in terms of ownership as indicated in the composite mean of 4.69 and percentile equivalent of 96. Ownership is the likelihood that someone will actually do anything to improve the situation, regardless of their formal responsibilities. It measures accountability, responsibility, action and engagement.

Among the indicators of AQ-ownership, the highest five that greatly characterize the respondents are:

Rank 1.5: The school heads keep themselves busy at work and act all requests at their tables as soon as possible to avoid delay. (Weighted Mean = 5.00 or Percentile Equivalent = 100)

Rank 1.5: They do everything they think important to meet all the deadlines and ensure smooth sailing of the organization they manage. (Weighted Mean = 5.00 or Percentile Equivalent = 100)

Rank 3.5: It is their obligation to carry forward the assigned task to them to a successful conclusion with authority to direct and take necessary action to ensure success. (Weighted Mean = 4.90 or Percentile Equivalent = 99)

Rank 3.5: They do all what they think best to accomplish the mandate provided to them. (Weighted Mean = 4.90 or Percentile Equivalent = 99)

This implies that the school heads of public schools at said province have very high AQ in terms of ownership. They greatly manifest the high level of accountability, responsibility, action and engagement. They keep themselves busy at work and act all requests at their table as soon as possible to avoid delay. They do everything they think important to meet all the deadlines and ensure smooth sailing of the organization they manage. It is their obligation to carry forward the assigned task to them to a successful conclusion with authority to direct and take necessary action to ensure success. They do all what they think best to accomplish the mandate provided to them

Moreover, as a leader, they consider themselves answerable/ accountable to all actions done by themselves and all their subordinates and the results. They don't blame others. They assume themselves the responsibilities. They attend meetings, engagements and prior commitments on time. They ensure that they attend all appointments they have in their schedule on time.

In case of conflict of schedule, they delegate such task to their assistant to attend such appointment to represent them without delay.

They participate as much as possible to all necessary activities of the organization they belong to show to their constituents that they are visible and ready to serve at any cost.

Furthermore, when problems at work come, most of them involve themselves to the speedy resolution of the problems. If something wrong happen, they do not blame the employees nor anybody who are implicated in that blunder. But they try to correct the system which may be the cause of that problem. Finally, majority of them also accept wholeheartedly all invitations to speak or grace programs or be a judge in a contest or to provide talks.

Table 13. *Frequency, Summation and Mean Distribution of Responses of Respondents to determine their Adversity Quotient in Terms of Reach*

<i>Indicators</i>		5	4	3	2	1	$\sum x$	$\sum xw$	Mean
1.	When problem arise at work, I try to solve it not on the surface but on a deeper analysis of that problem. I believe that a particular problem is interconnected with other problem.	6	4	0	0	0	10	46	4.60
		30	16	0	0	0			
2.	I know that assuming a leadership role is burdensome. Therefore I think leadership burden as part of life and assume it a blessing for further successes in life.	6	2	2	0	0	10	44	4.40
		30	8	6	0	0			
3.	Leadership is really stressful. That is why I always use various coping strategies to reduce the effect of stress to me and to the organization I manage.	6	3	1	0	0	10	45	4.50
		30	12	3	0	0			
4.	I do all possible ways to avoid worrying to anything which causes anxiety vexation or headache.	3	6	1	0	0	10	42	4.20
		15	24	3	0	0			
5.	I consider stresses at work as stepping stone to more successes in life and to more challenging endeavors to perform.	3	5	1	1	0	10	40	4.00
		15	20	3	2	0			
6.	I always alarm my subordinates or constituents in case impending problems or adversities are seen coming in.	4	4	2	0	0	10	42	4.20
		20	16	6	0	0			
7.	Despite of numerous problems I encounter at work, I try all my best to maintain my posture and my healthy capacity for vigorous activities.	4	5	1	0	0	10	43	4.30
		20	20	3	0	0			
8.	I always perform my work with motivated spirit, sustained strength, continued vigor, sprightliness and unabated energy.	7	3	0	0	0	10	47	4.70
		35	12	0	0	0			
9.	I consider that the problem of a lowliest employee is also a problem of the whole organization.	4	4	2	0	0	10	42	4.20
		20	16	6	0	0			
10.	I consider that the effort of a united group is much greater than the sum of the efforts of the individual members of the group.	7	2	1	0	0	10	46	4.60
		35	8	3	0	0			
Composite Mean									4.37

Table 13.1. *Mean and Percentile Distribution of Responses of Respondents to determine their Adversity Quotient in Terms of Reach*

<i>Indicators</i>		Weighted Mean	Percentile Equivalent	Verbal Description	Interpretation	Rank
1.	When problem arise at work, I try to solve it not on the surface but on a deeper analysis of that problem. I believe that a particular problem is interconnected with other problem.	4.60	96	Strongly agree	Very high	2.5
2.	I know that assuming a leadership role is burdensome. Therefore I think leadership burden as part of life and assume it a blessing for further successes in life.	4.40	94	Agree	High	5
3.	Leadership is really stressful. That is why I always use various coping strategies to reduce the effect of stress to me and to the organization I manage.	4.50	95	Strongly agree	Very high	4
4.	I do all possible ways to avoid worrying to anything which causes anxiety vexation or headache.	4.20	92	Agree	High	8
5.	I consider stresses at work as stepping stone to more successes in life and to more challenging endeavors to perform.	4.00	90	Agree	High	10
6.	I always alarm my subordinates or constituents in case impending problems or adversities are seen coming in.	4.20	92	Agree	High	8
7.	Despite of numerous problems I encounter at work, I try all my best to maintain my posture and my healthy capacity for vigorous activities.	4.30	93	Agree	High	6
8.	I always perform my work with motivated spirit, sustained strength, continued vigor, sprightliness and unabated energy.	4.70	97	Strongly agree	Very high	1
9.	I consider that the problem of a lowliest employee is also a problem of the whole organization.	4.20	92	Agree	High	8
10.	I consider that the effort of a united group is much greater than the sum of the efforts of the individual members of the group.	4.60	96	Strongly agree	Very high	2.5
Composite Mean		4.37	93	Agree	High	

Table 13 and Table 13.1 present the frequency, summation, mean and percentile distribution of responses of respondents to determine their adversity quotient in terms of reach. These tables show that the respondents agree that they have high level of adversity quotient in terms of reach as indicated in the composite mean of 4.37 and percentile equivalent of 93 Reach is the extent to which someone perceives an adversity will “reach into” and affect other aspects of the situation or beyond. It measures burden, stress, energy, and effort. It tends to have accumulative effect. Among the indicators of AQ-reach, the highest five that greatly characterize the respondents are:

Rank 1: The school heads always perform their work with motivated spirit, sustained strength, continued vigor, sprightliness and unabated energy. (Weighted Mean = 4.70 or Percentile Equivalent = 97)

Rank 2.5: When problem arise at work, they try to solve it not on the surface but on a deeper analysis of that problem. They believe that a particular problem is interconnected with other problem. (Weighted Mean = 4.60 or Percentile Equivalent = 96)

Rank 2.5: They consider that the effort of a united group is much greater than the sum of the efforts of the individual members of the group. (Weighted Mean = 4.60 or Percentile Equivalent = 96)

Rank 4: Leadership is really stressful. That is why they always use various coping strategies to reduce the effect of stress to them and to the organization they manage. (Weighted Mean = 4.50 or Percentile Equivalent = 95)

Rank 5: They know that assuming a leadership role is burdensome. Therefore I think leadership burden as part of life and assume it a blessing for further successes in life. (Weighted Mean = 4.40 or Percentile Equivalent = 94)

This implies that the school heads of public schools at said province have high AQ in terms of reach. They manifest the high level of proper handling of burden, stress, efforts and energy. They always perform their work with motivated spirit, sustained strength, continued vigor, sprightliness and unabated energy.

When problem arise at work, they try to solve it not on the surface but on a deeper analysis of that problem. They believe that a particular problem is interconnected with other problem. They consider that the effort of a united group is much greater than the sum of the efforts of the individual members of the group.

Moreover, leadership is really stressful. That is why they always use various coping strategies to reduce the effect of stress to them and to the organization they manage. A large number of them know that assuming a leadership role is burdensome. Therefore, they think leadership burden as part of life and assume it a blessing for further successes in life. Despite of numerous problems they encounter at work, they try all their best to maintain their posture and their healthy capacity for vigorous activities.

Furthermore, they do all possible ways to avoid worrying to anything which causes anxiety vexation or headache. They always alarm their subordinates or constituents in case impending problems or adversities are seen coming in. They consider that the problem of a lowliest employee is also a problem of the whole organization. Lastly, they consider stresses at work as stepping stone to more successes in life and to more challenging endeavors to perform.

Table 14. Frequency, Summation and Mean Distribution of Responses of Respondents to determine their Adversity Quotient in Terms of Endurance

Indicators	5	4	3	2	1	$\sum x$	$\sum xw$	Mean
1. For any problems, sorrows, affliction and downs in life, there are ups and comfort zones.	7	3	0	0	0	10	47	4.70
	35	12	0	0	0			
2. I always cherish that there is solution for every problem; and there is up for every down.	7	3	0	0	0	10	47	4.70
	35	12	0	0	0			
3. I strongly believe that good will ultimately triumph over evil.	8	2	0	0	0	10	48	4.80
	40	8	0	0	0			
4. I have the tendency to expect the best and see the best in all things.	5	4	1	0	0	10	44	4.40
	25	16	3	0	0			
5. I have the tendency to look on the more favorable side or to expect the most favorable outcome of events or conditions.	4	6	0	0	0	10	44	4.40
	20	24	0	0	0			
6. I always smile. I never frown. I cultivate the happy disposition in life. I'm cheerful always when I am at work especially when I'm in front of my constituents.	2	3	5	0	0	10	37	3.70
	10	12	15	0	0			
7. I have a persistent determination to do what is right despite of overwhelming political and organizational pressures that boost me to do the opposite.	5	5	0	0	0	10	45	4.50
	25	20	0	0	0			
8. I can endure all oppositions, criticisms, sarcasms, and all negative remarks regarding my personality, the way I lead people and how I manage and the decision I make.	3	6	1	0	0	10	42	4.20
	15	24	3	0	0			
9. I ignore all destructive criticisms that I receive but I welcome all constructive criticisms to improve myself and the way I manage the institution I belong.	5	4	1	0	0	10	44	4.40
	25	16	3	0	0			
10. I believe that I have the power, stamina, patience and long sufferance to withstand intense hardship and stress that I encounter in the performance of my work as a leader.	4	6	0	0	0	10	44	4.40
	20	24	0	0	0			
Composite Mean								4.42

Table 14.1. Mean and Percentile Distribution of Responses of Respondents to determine their Adversity Quotient in Terms of Endurance

	Indicators	Weighted Mean	Percentile Equivalent	Verbal Description	Interpretation	Rank
1.	For any problems, sorrows, affliction and downs in life, there are ups and comfort zones.	4.70	97	Strongly agree	Very high	2.5
2.	I always cherish that there is solution for every problem; and there is up for every down.	4.70	97	Strongly agree	Very high	2.5
3.	I strongly believe that good will ultimately triumph over evil.	4.80	98	Strongly agree	Very high	1
4.	I have the tendency to expect the best and see the best in all things.	4.40	94	Agree	High	6.5
5.	I have the tendency to look on the more favorable side or to expect the most favorable outcome of events or conditions.	4.40	94	Agree	High	6.5
6.	I always smile. I never frown. I cultivate the happy disposition in life. I'm cheerful always when I am at work especially when I'm in front of my constituents.	3.70	87	Agree	High	10
7.	I have a persistent determination to do what is right despite of overwhelming political and organizational pressures that boost me to do the opposite.	4.50	95	Strongly agree	Very high	4
8.	I can endure all oppositions, criticisms, sarcasms, and all negative remarks regarding my personality, the way I lead people and how I manage and the decision I make.	4.20	92	Agree	High	9
9.	I ignore all destructive criticisms that I receive but I welcome all constructive criticisms to improve myself and the way I manage the institution I belong.	4.40	94	Agree	High	6.5
10.	I believe that I have the power, stamina, patience and long sufferance to withstand intense hardship and stress that I encounter in the performance of my work as a leader.	4.40	94	Agree	High	6.5
Composite Mean		4.42	94	Agree	High	

Table 14 and Table 14.1 present the frequency, summation, mean and percentile distribution of responses of respondents to determine their adversity quotient in terms of endurance. These tables show that the respondents agree that they have high level of adversity quotient in terms of endurance as indicated in the composite mean of 4.42 and percentile equivalent of 94. Endurance is the length of time the individual perceives the situation/adversity will last, or endure. It measures hope, optimism, and willingness to persevere. Among the indicators of AQ- endurance, the highest five that greatly characterize the respondents are:

Rank 1: The school heads strongly believe that good will ultimately triumph over evil. (Weighted Mean = 4.80 or Percentile Equivalent = 98)

Rank 2.5: They strongly believe that for any problems, sorrows, affliction and downs in life, there are ups and comfort zones. (Weighted Mean = 4.70 or Percentile Equivalent = 97)

Rank 2.5: They always cherish that there is solution for every problem; and there is up for every down. (Weighted Mean = 4.70 or Percentile Equivalent = 97)

Rank 4: They have a persistent determination to do what is right despite of overwhelming political and organizational pressures that boost them to do the opposite. (Weighted Mean = 4.70 or Percentile Equivalent = 97)

This implies that the school heads of public schools at said province have high AQ in terms of endurance. They manifest high level of hope, optimism, and willingness to persevere. They strongly believe that good will ultimately triumph over evil. They also strongly believe that for any problems, sorrows, affliction and downs in life, there are ups and comfort zones. They always cherish that there is solution for every problem; and there is up for every down. They have a persistent determination to do what is right despite of overwhelming political and organizational pressures that boost them to do the opposite.

Moreover, they have the tendency to expect the best and see the best in all things. They have the tendency to look on the more favorable side or to expect the most favorable outcome of events or conditions.

Furthermore, majority of them ignore all destructive criticisms that they receive but they welcome all constructive criticisms to improve themselves and the way they manage the institutions they belong. They believe that they have the power, stamina, patience and long sufferance to withstand intense hardship and stress that they encounter in the performance of their work as a leader. Lastly, some of them always smile. They never frown. They cultivate the happy disposition in life. They are cheerful always when they are at work especially when they are in front of their constituents.

Table 15. Summary Table of Adversity Quotient Components' Ratings and Interpretation

AQ Components	Composite Mean	Percentile Equivalent	Verbal Description	Interpretation	Rank
Control	3.85	88	Agree	High	4
Ownership	4.69	96	Strongly agree	Very high	1
Reach	4.37	93	Agree	High	3
Endurance	4.42	94	Agree	High	2
Over-all Mean	4.33	93	Agree	High	

Table 15 presents the summary of adversity quotient components' ratings and interpretation. This table shows that the respondents as a whole are rated a composite mean of 4.33 which has a percentile equivalent of 93. It is verbally interpreted as high AQ. Among the components, ownership is the highest with the rating of 4.69 or percentile equivalent of 96; followed by endurance with the rating of 4.42 or percentile equivalent of 94 and reach with the rating of 4.37 or percentile equivalent of 93. This implies that the school heads of public schools at said province have a high level of Adversity Quotient.

Adversity quotient of the respondents be measured in terms of:

Internal Concerns

Table 16. Frequency, Summation and Mean Distribution of Responses of Respondents to Measure their Adversity Quotient in Terms of Internal Concerns-Personal Concerns

Indicators	5	4	3	2	1	$\sum x$	$\sum xw$	Mean
1. I experienced financial setbacks or loses.	5	3	2	0	0	10	43	4.30
	25	12	6	0	0			
2. I'm worried when I am criticized for the decision I have made.	1	2	2	3	2	10	27	2.70
	5	8	6	6	2			
3. I have accidentally deleted and could no longer recover very important file that I have worked on for a long time.	0	3	3	4	0	10	29	2.90
	0	12	9	8	0			
4. I and my loved ones seem to be drifting apart.	0	2	0	2	6	10	18	1.80
	0	8	0	4	6			
5. Someone I respect called me for advice.	2	6	2	0	0	10	40	4.00
	10	24	6	0	0			
6. I received an unexpected gift on my birthday.	3	5	2	0	0	10	41	4.10
	15	20	6	0	0			
7. My valued friend did not call on my birthday.	0	0	2	4	4	10	18	1.80
	0	0	6	8	4			
8. I have a heated argument with my spouse or special friend.	0	2	2	1	5	10	21	2.10
	0	8	6	2	5			
9. I were caught in a traffic jam on my way to a very important appointment.	0	4	3	1	2	10	29	2.90
	0	16	9	2	2			
10. I easily react on criticisms and opposing opinions.	0	1	2	6	1	10	23	2.30
	0	4	6	12	1			
11. My close friend became very ill.	1	2	3	1	3	10	27	2.70
	5	8	9	2	3			
12. I'm cautioned by my doctor regarding my physical health.	0	7	1	0	1	10	32	3.20
	0	28	3	0	1			
13. I placed several phone calls and sent messages, he/she never replied.	1	1	4	3	1	10	28	2.80
	5	4	12	6	1			
14. Someone close to me is diagnosed with cancer.	0	4	3	2	1	10	30	3.00
	0	16	9	4	1			
15. I missed the last trip.	0	2	2	3	3	10	23	2.30
	0	8	6	6	3			
16. I feel overloaded with work and that my job takes so much of my time.	0	3	3	2	2	10	27	2.70
	0	12	9	4	2			
Composite Mean								2.85

External Concerns

Table 16.1. Mean and Percentile Distribution of Responses of Respondents to Measure their Adversity Quotient in Terms of Internal Concerns-Personal Concerns

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Percentile Equivalent	Verbal Description	Interpretation	Rank
1. I experienced financial setbacks or loses.	4.30	93	Agree (Affects)	Low	1
2. I'm worried when I am criticized for the decision I have made.	2.70	77	Moderately agree (Moderately affects)	Average	10
3. I have accidentally deleted and could no longer	2.90	79	Moderately agree	Average	6.5

	recover very important file that I have worked on for a long time.				(Moderately affects)	
4.	I and my loved ones seem to be drifting apart.	1.80	68	Disagree	High	15.5
				(Does not affect)		
5.	Someone I respect called me for advice.	4.00	90	Agree (Affects)	Low	3
6.	I received an unexpected gift on my birthday.	4.10	91	Agree (Affects)	Low	2
7.	My valued friend did not call on my birthday.	1.80	68	Disagree	High	15.5
				(Does not affect)		
8.	I have a heated argument with my spouse or special friend.	2.10	71	Disagree	High	14
				(Does not affect)		
9.	I were caught in a traffic jam on my way to a very important appointment.	2.90	79	Moderately agree	Average	6.5
				(Moderately affects)		
10.	I easily react on criticisms and opposing opinions.	2.30	73	Disagree	High	12.5
				(Does not affect)		
11.	My close friend became very ill.	2.70	77	Moderately agree	Average	10
				(Moderately affects)		
12.	I'm cautioned by my doctor regarding my physical health.	3.20	82	Moderately agree	Average	4
				(Moderately affects)		
13.	I placed several phone calls and sent messages, he/she never replied.	2.80	78	Moderately agree	Average	8
				(Moderately affects)		
14.	Someone close to me is diagnosed with cancer.	3.00	80	Moderately agree	Average	5
				(Moderately affects)		
15.	I missed the last trip.	2.30	73	Disagree	High	12.5
16.	I feel overloaded with work and that my job takes so much of my time.	2.70	77	Moderately agree	Average	10
				(Moderately affects)		
	Composite Mean	2.85	78	Moderately agree	Average	
				(Moderately affects)		

Table 16 and Table 16.1 present the frequency, mean and percentile distribution of responses of respondents to measure their adversity quotient in terms of internal concerns-personal concerns. These tables show that the respondents moderately agree that the indicators regarding internal concerns more specifically on personal concerns affect them as indicated in the composite mean of 2.85 and percentile equivalent of 78. This indicates that the respondents have moderate level of adversity quotient in regards to internal concerns more specifically on personal concerns. The highest five indicators which have moderate to substantial effect to the respondents are:

Rank 1: The school heads experienced financial setbacks or loses. (Weighted Mean = 4.30 or Percentile Equivalent = 93)

Rank 2: They received an unexpected gift on their birthday. (Weighted Mean = 4.10 or Percentile Equivalent = 91)

Rank 3: Someone they respect called them for advice. (Weighted Mean = 4.00 or Percentile Equivalent = 90)

Rank 4: They are cautioned by their doctor regarding their physical health. (Weighted Mean = 3.20 or Percentile Equivalent = 82)

Rank 5: Someone close to them is diagnosed with cancer. (Weighted Mean = 3.00 or Percentile Equivalent = 80).

This implies that the school heads of selected public schools at said province have average level of adversity quotient pertaining to internal concerns more specifically on personal concerns. They are easily affected when it comes to financial setbacks, unexpected gift, and unexpected call from whom they respect and in regards to their health. However, generally, they are moderately affected by internal adversity concerns more specifically on personal concerns.

Table 17. Frequency, Summation and Mean Distribution of Responses of Respondents to Measure their Adversity Quotient in Terms of Internal Concerns-Work-related Concerns

	Indicators	5	4	3	2	1	$\sum x$	$\sum xw$	Mean
1.	My latest marketing strategies get more employees backfired.	0	1	1	5	3	10	20	2.00
		0	4	3	10	3			
2.	My subordinates ignored my attempt to discuss an important issue.	0	1	1	4	4	10	19	1.90
		0	4	3	8	4			
3.	My subordinates responded unfavorably to my latest ideas.	0	1	2	4	3	10	21	2.10
		0	4	6	8	3			
4.	My workplace is under staffed	1	2	1	2	4	10	24	2.40
		5	8	3	4	4			
5.	My subordinates were unreceptive to my ideas, proposals, policies, etc.	0	1	2	4	3	10	21	2.10
		0	4	6	8	3			
6.	I received a very negative feedback from my trusted subordinates.	0	0	2	6	2	10	20	2.00
		0	0	6	12	2			
7.	The meeting I called and presided was a waste of time.	0	0	1	5	4	10	17	1.70
		0	0	3	10	4			

8.	I was unable to take the most needed vacation because of too much work.	0	4	4	2	0	10	32	3.20
		0	16	12	4	0			
9.	My school /organization is not meeting its projected goals, mission and vision.	0	6	2	1	1	10	33	3.20
		0	24	6	2	1			
10.	My superior adamantly disapproved/disagreed with my decisions.	0	4	4	1	1	10	31	3.10
		0	16	12	2	1			
Composite Mean									2.37

Table 17.1. Mean and Percentile Distribution of Responses of Respondents to Measure their Adversity Quotient in Terms of Internal Concerns-Work-related Concerns

	Indicators	Weighted Mean	Percentile Equivalent	Verbal Description	Interpretation	Rank
1.	My latest marketing strategies get more employees backfired.	2.00	70	Disagree (Does not affect)	High	7.5
2.	My subordinates ignored my attempt to discuss an important issue.	1.90	69	Disagree (Does not affect)	High	9
3.	My subordinates responded unfavorably to my latest ideas.	2.10	71	Disagree (Does not affect)	High	5.5
4.	My workplace is under staffed	2.40	74	Disagree (Does not affect)	High	4
5.	My subordinates were unreceptive to my ideas, proposals, policies, etc.	2.10	71	Disagree (Does not affect)	High	5.5
6.	I received a very negative feedback from my trusted subordinates.	2.00	70	Disagree (Does not affect)	High	7.5
7.	The meeting I called and presided was a waste of time.	1.70	69	Disagree (Does not affect)	High	10
8.	I was unable to take the most needed vacation because of too much work.	3.20	82	Moderately agree (Moderately affects)	Average	1.5
9.	My school /organization is not meeting its projected goals, mission and vision.	3.20	82	Moderately agree (Moderately affects)	Average	1.5
10.	My superior adamantly disapproved/disagreed with my decisions.	3.10	81	Moderately agree (Moderately affects)	Average	3
Composite Mean		2.37	73	Disagree (Does not affect)	High	

Table 17 and Table 17A present frequency, summation, mean and percentile distribution of responses of respondents to measure their adversity quotient in terms of internal concerns-work-related concerns. These tables show that the respondents generally disagree that the indicators pertaining to internal concerns specifically on work-related concerns affect them as indicated in the composite mean of 2.37 and percentile equivalent of 73. This indicates that the respondents have high level of adversity quotient pertaining on internal concerns, specifically on work-related concerns. Among the indicators, the highest three which have moderate effect to the respondents are:

Rank 1.5: The school heads were unable to take the most needed vacation because of too much work. (Weighted Mean =3.20 or Percentile Equivalent =82)

Rank 1.5: Their school /organization is not meeting its projected goals, mission and vision. (Weighted Mean =3.20 or Percentile Equivalent =82)

Rank 3: Their superior adamantly disapproved/disagreed with their decisions. (Weighted Mean =3.00 or Percentile Equivalent =80)

This implies that the school heads of selected schools at said province have high level of AQ- internal concerns more specifically on work-related concerns. They are not affected by work related concerns. However, they are moderately affected by inability to take the most needed vacation because of too much work; not meeting the school’s projected goals, mission and vision; and adamant disapproval/ disagreement of their superior with their decisions.

Table 18. Frequency, Summation and Mean Distribution of Responses of Respondents to Measure their Adversity Quotient in Terms of External Concerns

	Indicators	5	4	3	2	1	$\sum x$	$\sum xw$	Mean
1.	I’m worried with the latest news in media.	0	2	5	3	0	10	25	2.50
		0	8	15	2	0			
2.	I’m bothered when a politician opposes my decision I made.	0	0	3	2	5	10	18	1.80
		0	0	9	4	5			
3.	I want to do right but my colleagues in other schools do the opposite.	0	0	3	4	3	10	20	2.00
		0	0	9	8	3			
4.	I knew that one of my family members was one among the casualties in the tragic	0	2	2	3	3	10	19	1.90

accidents.	0	4	6	6	3			
5. I heard a negative gossip against me from my neighbor.	0	0	5	1	4	10	21	2.10
	0	0	15	2	4			
6. The people in the community I live nearby snub me when I meet them.	0	0	1	5	4	10	17	1.70
	0	0	3	10	4			
7. The people in a big political gathering shouted “BOO” to me when they saw me walking towards them.	0	0	1	5	4	10	17	1.70
	0	0	3	10	4			
8. I was charged with various administrative, criminal and civil cases.	1	2	0	0	7	10	20	2.00
	5	8	0	0	7			
9. I was falsely accused in a broadsheet newspaper of graft and corruption.	1	2	0	0	7	10	20	2.00
	5	8	0	0	7			
10. A powerful politician called me to his office and lambasted me with anger and humiliation.	2	1	0	0	7	10	21	2.10
	10	4	0	0	7			
11. I was trapped outside of my house with storms and high flood.	2	0	2	0	6	10	22	2.20
	10	0	6	0	6			
12. My car was damaged by a vehicle when travelling home.	2	0	2	0	6	10	22	2.20
	10	0	6	0	6			
13. I was held up by an unknown robber.	3	1	0	0	6	10	25	2.50
	15	4	0	0	6			
14. When going to a church, the priest or pastor called me by name and severely reprimanded me of charges I think I’m totally innocent in front of many church members.	3	0	0	0	7	10	22	2.20
	15	0	0	0	7			
15. I received a document from the Ombudsman or from the court judge serving me a 3-month preventive suspension starting next week.	2	1	0	0	7	10	21	2.10
	10	4	0	0	7			
Composite Mean								2.07

Table 18.1. Mean and Percentile Distribution of Responses of Respondents to Measure their Adversity Quotient in Terms of External Concerns

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Percentile Equivalent	Verbal Description	Interpretation	Rank
1. I’m worried with the latest news in media.	2.50	75	Moderately agree	Average	1.5
2. I’m bothered when a politician opposes my decision I made.	1.80	68	Disagree	High	13
3. I want to do right but my colleagues in other universities/colleges do the opposite.	2.00	70	Disagree	High	10
4. I knew that one of my family members was one among the casualties in the tragic accidents.	1.90	69	Disagree (Does not affect)	High	12
5. I heard a negative gossip against me from my neighbour.	2.10	71	Disagree (Does not affect)	High	7
6. The people in the community I live nearby snub me when I meet them.	1.70	67	Disagree (Does not affect)	High	14.5
7. The people in a big political gathering shouted “BOO” to me when they saw me walking towards them.	1.70	67	Disagree (Does not affect)	High	14.5
8. I was charged with various administrative, criminal and civil cases.	2.00	70	Disagree (Does not affect)	High	10
9. I was falsely accused in a broadsheet newspaper of graft and corruption.	2.00	70	Disagree (Does not affect)	High	10
10. A powerful politician called me to his office and lambasted me with anger and humiliation.	2.10	71	Disagree (Does not affect)	High	7
11. I was trapped outside of my house with storms and high flood.	2.20	72	Disagree (Does not affect)	High	4
12. My car was damaged by a vehicle when travelling home.	2.20	72	Disagree (Does not affect)	High	4
13. I was held up by an unknown robber.	2.50	75	Moderately agree	Average	1.5
14. When going to a church, the priest or pastor called me by name and severely reprimanded me of charges I think I’m totally innocent in front of many church members.	2.20	72	Disagree (Does not affect)	High	4
15. I received a document from the Ombudsman/or from a court judge serving me a 3-month preventive suspension starting next week.	2.10	71	Disagree (Does not affect)	High	7
Composite Mean	2.07	70	Disagree	High	

Table 18 and Table 18.1 present the mean and percentile distribution of responses of respondents to measure their adversity quotient in terms of external concerns. These tables show that the respondents generally disagree that the indicators in external concerns affect them as indicated in the composite mean of 2.07 and percentile equivalent of 70. This also indicates that the respondents have high level

of adversity quotient in terms of external concerns. However, the respondents are moderately affected by being worried with the latest news in media (Weighted Mean = 2.50 or Percentile Equivalent = 75) and being held up by an unknown robber (Weighted Mean = 2.50 or Percentile Equivalent = 75).

This implies that the school heads of selected public schools at said province have high level of adversity quotient. They are generally not affected by external adversity concerns except in being moderately affected with the latest news in media and being held up by an unknown robber.

Table 19. Summary Table on Adversity Quotient on Internal and External Concerns

Adversity Concerns	Composite Mean	Percentile Equivalent	Verbal Description	Interpretation	Rank
Internal Concerns-Personal Concerns	2.85	78	Moderately agree (Moderately affects)	Average	1
Internal Concerns-Work-related Concerns	2.37	73	Disagree (Does not affect)	High	2
External Concerns	2.07	70	Disagree	High	3
Over-all Mean	2.43	74	Disagree	High	

Table 19 presents the summary on adversity quotient on internal and external concerns. This table shows that the respondents generally disagree that they are affected by internal and external adversity concerns as indicated in the over-all mean of 2.43 and percentile equivalent of 74 which is interpreted as having high level of adversity quotient. However, they are moderately affected by internal adversity concerns more specifically on personal concerns. This implies that the school heads of selected public schools at said province generally have high level of adversity quotient pertaining to internal and external concerns.

Significant relationship on the responses of the school heads regarding adversity quotient when they are grouped according to demographic profile

In terms of Age

Table 20. Data Needed for the Computation of Spearman Rho-Age vs. AQ-CORE

Age (1)	AQ-CORE Rating	r1	r2	D	D2
41 to 45	4.47	5	2	3	9
46 to 50	4.55	4	1	3	9
51 to 55	4.32	3	3	0	0
56 to 60	3.83	2	5	-3	9
61 and above	4.40	1	4	-3	9
Total n =5					∑ D2=36

$r_s = 1 - \frac{(6\sum D^2)}{N^3 - N}$
 $r_s = 1 - \frac{(6)(36)}{(5^3 - 5)} = 1 - \frac{(216)}{120} = 1 - 1.80 = -0.8$ High Negative correlation

Table 21. Spearman rho, Decision and Interpretation

n	Spearman rho	t-value	Decision	Interpretation
10	-0.8	Computed t-value =3.77 Tabular value= 2.306 at 0.05 level of significance	Reject null Hypothesis	Significant

To test the significance of r-value, t-value is required to be used.
 $t\text{-value} = r \times \text{square root of } \frac{(n-2)}{1-r^2} = -0.8 \times \text{square root of } \frac{(10-2)}{1-(-0.8)^2} = \text{square root of } (8/0.36) \times (-0.8) = -3.77 = 3.77$
 $df = 8$ at 0.05 level of significance.

Tables 20 and 21 present the statistical data for computation of Spearman rho correlation coefficient, and t-value to determine the significant relationship between adversity quotient and age or when the respondents are grouped according to age bracket.

The tables clearly show that there is significant negative relationship or correlation between age and adversity quotient as indicated in the computed spearman rho of 0.80 and t-test value of 3.77 which is higher than the tabular t-value of 2.306. This implies that the younger the age, the greater is the adversity quotient of the school heads.

In terms of Civil Status

Table 22. Data Needed for the Computation of Spearman Rho- Civil Status vs. AQ-CORE

Highest Educational Attainment (1)	AQ-CORE Rating (2)	r1	r2	D	D2
Single	4.25	3	3	0	0
Married	4.45	2	1	1	1
Widow	4.35	1	2	-1	1
Total n =3					∑ D2=2

$r_s = 1 - \frac{(6\sum D^2)}{N^3 - N}$
 $r_s = 1 - \frac{(6)(2)}{(3^3 - 3)} = 1 - \frac{(12)}{24} = 1 - 1.5 = -0.5$ Medium Negative correlation

Table 23. Spearman rho, Decision and Interpretation

<i>n</i>	<i>Spearman rho</i>	<i>t-value</i>	<i>Decision</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
6	-0.5	Computed t-value =1.15 Tabular value= 2.776 at 0.05 level of significance	Accept null Hypothesis	Not Significant

To test the significance of *r-value*, *t-value* is required to be used.
 $t\text{-value} = r \times \text{square root of } (n-2)/1-r^2 = -0.5 \times \text{square root of } (6-2)/1-(-0.5)^2 = \text{square root of } (4/0.75) \times (-0.5) = 1.15$
 $df = 4$ at 0.05 level of significance

Tables 22 and 23 present the statistical data for computation of Spearman rho correlation coefficient, and t-value to determine the significant relationship between adversity quotient and civil status or when the respondents are grouped according to civil status. The tables clearly show that there is no significant relationship or correlation between civil status and adversity quotient as indicated in the computed spearman rho of 0.5 and t-test value of 1.15 which is lower than the tabular t-value of 2.776. This implies that the civil status is not correlated to adversity quotient or civil status is not a predictor of AQ.

Educational Attainment

Table 24. Data Needed for the Computation of Spearman Rho- Educational Attainment vs. AQ-CORE

<i>Educational Attainment (1)</i>	<i>AQ-CORE Rating (2)</i>	<i>r1</i>	<i>r2</i>	<i>D</i>	<i>D2</i>
MA Degree Holder	4.37	3	2	1	1
With Doctorate Units	4.44	2	1	1	1
Doctorate Degree Holder	4.26	1	3	-2	4
Total n=3					$\sum D2=6$

$rs = 1 - (6\sum D2)/(N3-N)$
 $rs = 1 - (6)(6)/(33-3) = 1 - (36)/24 = 1 - 1.5 = -0.5$ Medium Negative correlation

Table 25. Spearman rho, Decision and Interpretation

<i>n</i>	<i>Spearman rho</i>	<i>t-value</i>	<i>Decision</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
6	-0.5	Computed t-value =1.15 Tabular value= 2.776 at 0.05 level of significance	Accept null Hypothesis	Not Significant

To test the significance of *r-value*, *t-value* is required to be used.
 $t\text{-value} = r \times \text{square root of } (n-2)/1-r^2 = -0.5 \times \text{square root of } (6-2)/1-(-0.5)^2 = \text{square root of } (4/0.75) \times (-0.5) = 1.15$
 $df = 4$ at 0.05 level of significance.

Tables 24 and 25 present the statistical data for computation of Spearman rho correlation coefficient, and t-value to determine the significant relationship between adversity quotient and highest educational attainment or when the respondents are grouped according to educational attainment. The tables clearly show that there is no significant relationship or correlation between highest educational attainment and adversity quotient as indicated in the computed spearman rho of 0.5 and t-test value of 1.15 which is lower than the tabular t-value of 2.776. This implies that the highest educational attainment is not correlated to adversity quotient or highest educational attainment is not a predictor of AQ.

Approximate Monthly Salary

Table 26. Data Needed for the Computation of Spearman Rho- Approximate Monthly Net Salary vs. AQ-CORE

<i>Approximate Monthly Salary</i>	<i>AQ-CORE Rating (2)</i>	<i>r1</i>	<i>r2</i>	<i>D</i>	<i>D2</i>
30,001 to 35,000	4.39	4	2	2	4
35,001-40,000	4.38	3	3	0	0
40,001-45,000	4.68	2	1	1	1
50,001 and above	4.32	1	4	-3	9
Total n=3					$\sum D2=14$

$rs = 1 - (6\sum D2)/(N3-N)$
 $rs = 1 - (6)(14)/(43-4) = 1 - (84)/60 = 1 - 1.4 = -0.4$ Low Negative correlation

Table 27. Spearman rho, Decision and Interpretation

<i>n</i>	<i>Spearman rho</i>	<i>t-value</i>	<i>Decision</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
8	-0.4	Computed t-value =1.07 Tabular value= 2.447 at 0.05 level of significance	Accept null Hypothesis	Not Significant

To test the significance of *r-value*, *t-value* is required to be used.
 $t\text{-value} = r \times \text{square root of } (n-2)/1-r^2 = -0.4 \times \text{square root of } (8-2)/1-(-0.4)^2 = \text{square root of } (6/0.84) \times (-0.4) = -1.07/ = 1.07$
 $df = 6$ at 0.05 level of significance.

Tables 26 and 27 present the statistical data for computation of Spearman rho correlation coefficient, and t-value to determine the significant relationship between adversity quotient and approximate monthly net salary or when the respondents are grouped according to approximate monthly net salary. The tables clearly show that there is no significant relationship or correlation between approximate monthly salary and adversity quotient as indicated in the computed spearman rho of -0.4 and t-test value of 1.07 which is lower than the tabular t-value of 2.447. This implies that the approximate monthly salary is not correlated to adversity quotient or approximate

monthly salary is not a predictor of AQ.

Suggested management guides and techniques may be formulated to augment and sustain their level of adversity quotient

Here are the suggested formulated management guides and techniques to augment/improve and sustain the level of adversity quotient:

Educational qualification is not a predictor of adversity quotient. Therefore, higher educational attainment is not a guarantee that an educational leader can withstand all trials, tests and troubles in life- Although higher educational qualification is an advantage especially for educational leadership especially as a school head in public school. However, it is independent from having high adversity quotient. High adversity quotient maybe a product of long experiences as a leader and a product of many trials, tests and challenges in life.

Age does not matter when it comes to adversity quotient- Based on the results of the study, the higher the age, the lower the adversity quotient. It perplexes this researcher on how come such happen. It only proves that age does not matter. Leadership is not dependent on age. Having adversity quotient is not obtained by the passing of time but on the density of problems and challenges met and on the determination and upbringing of leaders in dealing and resolving the problems encountered.

Civil Status is not a predictor of adversity quotient- Whether a person is married or not, has no count for having higher level of adversity quotient.

Money or wealth is not a predictor of adversity quotient- Accumulating more wealth does not guarantee for attaining higher level of adversity quotient. Money serves only as satisfaction factor. But it has no impact on having an endurance and resilience to achieve success.

Adversity Quotient measures the capacity of the person to deal and respond with the adversities of life such as stress, difficulties, problems, and challenges in life- Adversity quotient has four components such as control, ownership, reach and endurance. Adversity quotient refers to how a person deals with work stresses, intriguing problems and adversities encountered in the work place both internal and external and how he withstands adversity and his ability to triumph over it. Control refers to is the extent to which someone perceives they can influence whatever happens next. It determines resilience, health, and tenacity. Ownership refers to is the likelihood that someone will actually do anything to improve the situation, regardless of their formal responsibilities. It measures accountability, responsibility, action and engagement. Reach refers to is the extent to which someone perceives an adversity will “reach into” and affect other aspects of the situation or beyond. It measures burden, stress, energy, and effort. It tends to have accumulative effect. Endurance, on the other hand refers to the length of time the individual perceives the situation/adversity will last, or endure. It measures hope, optimism, and willingness to persevere.

Conclusions

The findings of the study drew the following conclusions

Demographic Profile- All of the respondents are forties to sixties. All of them are female- a proof that education field is dominated by female. Majority are married and have doctorate units. Almost half of the respondents reside in A. The rest reside in various places in Hinabangan, Western Samar. Majority of the respondents are Roman Catholic. All respondents have more than 2 years of being a school head and have more than 2 years of administrative experiences. Majority of them receive an approximate monthly net salary of more than fifty thousand pesos.

Adversity Quotient-CORE- The school heads of selected public schools in Hinabangan, Western Samar have a high level of Adversity Quotient.

Adversity Quotient-Internal and External Concerns- The school heads of selected public schools at said province generally have high level of adversity quotient pertaining to internal and external concerns.

Significant Correlation- In terms of age among the deans of nursing schools, the younger the age, the greater is the adversity quotient. In terms of civil status, highest educational attainment, and approximate monthly gross salary among the deans, these are not correlated to adversity quotient or they are not a predictor of AQ.

Suggested Guides- Here are the suggested formulated management guides and techniques to augment/improve and sustain the level of adversity quotient:

Educational qualification is not a predictor of adversity quotient. Therefore, higher educational attainment is not a guarantee that an educational leader can withstand all trials, tests and troubles in life.

Age does not matter when it comes to adversity quotient.

Civil Status is not a predictor of adversity quotient.

Money or wealth is not a predictor of adversity quotient- Adversity Quotient measures the capacity of the person to deal and respond with the adversities of life such as stress, difficulties, problems, and challenges in life.

In the light of the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

This researcher recommends that this study be done in other educational institutions both public and private schools not included in this study. This suggests that it may be done somewhere in Samar and other parts of the Philippines. This study can be replicated using different sets of respondents from other schools to externally validate this study, whether this study is still true to other sets of respondents. She also desires to have another study done by other researchers considering the more expanded socio-demographic profile.

It is also recommended the use of the modified AQ-CORE questionnaire by other educational leaders especially in other fields of specialization.

The AQ-internal and external concerns can also be used to validate the AQ-CORE. They must have similar ratings to establish their validity and reliability. In this study, the researcher proved that similar ratings were made.

It is also recommended the use of statistical measure on significant difference aside from significant relationship as used in this study.

The stated suggested guides are strongly recommended to be used to have better AQ, higher administrative leadership and higher school performance as reflected in the school achievement test results.

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